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RESEARCH-ARTICLE

Optimizing Neighborhoods for Fair Top-N Recommendation

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ABSTRACT

We address demographic bias in *neighborhood-learning* models for collaborative filtering recommendations. Despite their superior ranking performance, these methods can learn neighborhoods that inadvertently foster discriminatory patterns. Little work exists in this area, highlighting an important research gap. A notable yet solitary effort, *Balanced Neighborhood Sparse Linear Method (BNSLIM)* aims at balancing neighborhood influence across different demographic groups. Yet, BNSLIM is hampered by computational inefficiency, and its rigid balancing approach often impacts accuracy. In that vein, we introduce two novel algorithms. The first, an enhancement of BNSLIM, incorporates the *Alternating Direction Method of Multipliers (ADMM)* to optimize all similarities concurrently, greatly reducing training time. The second, *Fairly Sparse Linear Regression (FSLR)*, induces controlled sparsity in neighborhoods to reveal correlations among different demographic groups, achieving comparable efficiency while being more accurate. Their performance is evaluated using standard exposure metrics alongside a new metric for user coverage disparities. Our experiments cover various applications, including a novel exploration of bias in course recommendations by teachers' country development status. Our results show the effectiveness of our algorithms in imposing fairness compared to BNSLIM and other well-known fairness approaches.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Information systems** → **Recommender systems**; • **Computing methodologies** → **Learning linear models**.

KEYWORDS

balanced neighborhoods, collaborative filtering, fairness, neighborhood learning, recommender systems, sparse linear models

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1 INTRODUCTION

Recommenders have become indispensable decision-making tools across diverse domains, from e-commerce to healthcare [17, 18]. As a result, their unbiased functioning has become a key concern for the scientific community. To mitigate bias, various dimensions of fairness have been explored in the literature [30, 38]. *Individual fairness* aims for similar individuals to be treated similarly, whereas *group fairness* aims for different groups to be treated similarly. These groups are often divided into *protected* and *non-protected*, with the former being subject to bias. Fairness in recommenders also requires an understanding of their *multi-stakeholder* nature [5]. *Consumer fairness (C-fairness)* looks at fairness from the side of the users, whereas *Provider fairness (P-fairness)* looks at fairness from the side of the items. Fairness benefits may also vary: *exposure* refers to the uniformity with which items or item groups are presented across all users or user groups, and *effectiveness* refers to the degree to which an exposure is effective [11]. Based on the stage at which fairness considerations take place, approaches can be categorized into: *pre-processing*, *in-processing*, and *post-processing*.

Collaborative Filtering (CF) recommenders offer item suggestions based on past user-item interactions, such as ratings or clicks [24]. While traditional CF methods use predefined similarity measures to compute user-user or item-item similarities, neighborhood-learning CF models [34], considered state-of-the-art (SOTA) [1, 15], dynamically derive these similarities from the interaction data. The SOTA models, *Sparse Linear Methods (SLIM)* [35] and *Embarrassingly Shallow AutoEncoders (EASE)* [41], differ in approach. SLIM estimates sparse similarities to preclude less important neighbors, while EASE estimates dense similarities to include correlated neighbors. Given that similarities may be derived from imbalanced interactions, a critical question arises: *do the computed similarities unwittingly sustain or exacerbate existing biases?*

Imbalanced interactions between different user or item demographics render these methods vulnerable to demographic bias, in which certain user or item demographic groups are unfairly treated over others [7]. We give two motivating examples that highlight demographic bias in user-based and item-based methods.

User-neighborhood example. On an academic platform where students can be grouped based on their gender as either females or males, assume a preference imbalance: females mainly engage with the humanities, while males are more inclined towards STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics). Consider a female student who has a balanced interest in both the humanities and STEM. If her neighborhood mostly includes female students, her recommendations are likely to favor courses in the humanities, potentially overlooking her interests in STEM.

Item-neighborhood example. On an academic platform where courses can be grouped based on the country of the teacher, assume a preference imbalance: courses by teachers from developed countries receive more interactions than those from developing countries. Consider a user engaging with a course from the developed country group. If its neighborhood mostly includes courses by teachers from developed countries, the user’s recommendations are likely to favor such courses, potentially overlooking related courses by teachers from developing countries.

In that vein, the *balanced neighborhoods* concept was introduced, aimed at balanced group representation in user or item neighborhoods for C- or P-fairness, respectively, as realized by *Balanced Neighborhood SLIM (BNSLIM)* [7] that adds the *balanced regularization term* into SLIM. BNSLIM learns similarities such that, within each neighborhood, the cumulative similarity across neighbors of the protected group is equal to that of the non-protected group. For our user-neighborhood example, this means having a balance between the influence of female and male neighbors. For our item-neighborhood example, this means having a balance between the influence of courses by teachers from developed and developing countries. BNSLIM employs *Coordinate Descent (CD)* for optimizing each similarity individually, which is impractical for large datasets. To partly address this, during each CD step, the algorithm focuses solely on the closest neighbors, which are predefined and fixed throughout the algorithm [6]. Still, the computational burden is significant [3]. More crucially, such static neighbor selection potentially harms the intended balancing effect due to a lack of group diversity; thus, the true potential of balancing neighborhoods for fairness remains unverified to its full extent. Lastly, BNSLIM’s rigid balancing approach may adversely affect personalization by increasing (decreasing) the similarity scores with irrelevant (relevant) neighbors just for the sake of influence balance.

Overcoming these limitations, we present two novel in-processing algorithms for group fairness to mitigate demographic bias in neighborhood learning. We focus on the benefit of exposure¹, reducing exposure disparities in top-N recommendation lists: C-fairness involves balancing the exposure of item groups across user groups, while P-fairness involves balancing the exposure of item groups within the top-N lists of all users. Our algorithms optimize user or item neighborhoods for C- or P-fairness, respectively. The first algorithm, *BNSLIM_{ADMM}*, tackles the efficiency bottleneck of BNSLIM by allowing simultaneous optimization of all similarities. The second, *Fairly Sparse Linear Regression (FSLR)*, induces controlled sparsity in neighborhoods, ensuring representation by demographically varied, yet *correlated*, counterparts to improve fairness while preserving personalization. This is achieved by integrating a novel regularization term into EASE. For our user-neighborhood example, this means that the recommendations of the female student will largely be influenced by the preferences of similar male students. For our item-neighborhood example, this means that the recommendations of the user will largely be influenced by similar courses from the developing countries group. Both algorithms employ the *Alternating Direction Method of Multipliers (ADMM)* for its ability to decompose complex optimization problems and convergence properties [4].

¹In this work, the terms *exposure* and *visibility* are used interchangeably to describe how frequently items appear in top-N recommendation lists.

We ran extensive experiments across various recommendation domains: movies (Movielens 1M [19]), music (LastFM 1K [8]), courses (COCO [12]), and books (Goodreads [44]). We explore how teachers’ country development status affects course recommendations, a P-fairness scenario that (to the best of our knowledge) has not previously been studied. Furthermore, we study fairness not only by measuring exposure disparities of item groups across all users or user groups (our primary fairness goal), but also by measuring disparities in the coverage of user groups (in terms of the item categories they access through recommendations) or item groups. For the latter, we present *User-coverage Parity (u-Parity)*, a novel exposure metric for C-fairness that measures the difference in percentages of protected and non-protected users covered by each item category. Results show that under the given fairness goals, our algorithms outperform other leading fairness-aware models [7, 9, 46] in balancing personalization and fairness, with FSLR showing superior accuracy than *BNSLIM_{ADMM}*. Notably, *BNSLIM_{ADMM}* significantly reduces training time by around 99%, compared to BNSLIM. Overall, our algorithms are uniquely capable of achieving satisfactory results for both C- and P-fairness.

Our contributions are summarized as follows:

- (1) We introduce *BNSLIM_{ADMM}*, a faster implementation of BNSLIM that updates all similarities concurrently.
- (2) We introduce FSLR, a novel model that induces controlled sparsity in neighborhoods, ensuring representation by demographically varied, yet correlated, counterparts to improve fairness while preserving personalization.
- (3) We present u-Parity, a novel exposure metric for C-fairness that measures the disparity in coverage percentages between protected and non-protected users across item categories.
- (4) We study the influence of teachers’ country development status in course recommendations, offering insights into a previously unexplored P-fairness application.
- (5) We provide empirical evidence across diverse datasets, comparing *BNSLIM_{ADMM}* and FSLR to other established fair recommendation models [7, 9, 46], showing their superiority in balancing accuracy and fairness.

2 RELATED WORK

Fairness definitions. In recommenders, fairness definitions are shaped by task (i.e., rating prediction or ranking) and fairness type (i.e., individual or group, C- or P-fairness). In the rating-prediction task, C- and P-fairness aim to balance average ratings or prediction errors across user or item groups [22, 46], while individual C-fairness aims to minimize prediction error variance across all pairs of users (individual C-fairness) [39]. In the ranking task, P-fairness aims to balance the exposure of item groups [7, 16, 48], or their coverage in top-N recommendation lists [29], whereas C-fairness aims to balance the exposure of items [9] or item groups [7], or ensure comparable relevance levels [13, 26], across user groups. We target group fairness in top-N recommendation lists (rankings), focusing on either C-fairness (balancing the exposure of item groups across user groups) or P-fairness (balancing the exposure of item groups within the top-N recommendation lists of all users).

Fairness-aware CF methods typically fall into three categories: **Fairness-aware embedding methods**. These methods learn bias-free embeddings. [20–22] introduced regularizers to decouple predicted ratings from sensitive attributes. [46] focused on the dependency of those attributes with prediction errors. [47] proposed the use of a sensitive embedding matrix along with an orthogonality regularizer. [48] proposed a ranking model based on adversarial learning to handle item under-recommendation. [45] introduced a user model comprising a bias-aware embedding built through sensitive attribute prediction and a bias-free embedding built on adversarial learning. [27] enabled users to define their sensitive attributes, using adversarial learning for rankings that are personalized yet free from these attributes' influence. *Instead of purifying the learned embeddings from sensitive attributes, our work regulates the neighborhood distribution of users or items to promote fairness.*

Data-driven fairness methods. Data augmentation approaches mitigate unfairness using a dual-optimization strategy, optimizing the model and fake data, such as user profiles [39] or interactions [9], concurrently. However, each method generates fake data differently: [39] tries to meet predefined fairness objectives, whereas [9], independent of fairness metrics, employs two hypotheses to balance interactions between user groups. Instead of increasing the size of the dataset, a different approach is to modify the user or item relationships. BNSLIM balances influences within user or item neighborhoods, aiming for equal representation of protected and non-protected members within a neighborhood [7]. *Like BNSLIM, our algorithms target C- or P-fairness by optimizing neighborhoods.*

Rebalancing methods. These methods mitigate unfairness by rebalancing the input or output of recommenders. [14, 31] studied data resampling techniques to adjust the representation of protected and non-protected user groups, mitigating demographic bias. [40] proposed a probabilistic re-ranker for balancing item groups' exposure. [29] proposed a re-ranker for balancing users' ranking accuracy and provider diversity. [26] introduced a re-ranking framework for balancing ranking accuracy across user groups with different activity levels. [33] introduced a framework that extends the concept of [26] to also balance the exposure of long-tail and short-head items. *We address fairness directly during the processing stage, eliminating the need for further re-sampling or re-ranking.*

3 PRELIMINARIES

This section provides an overview of the neighborhood-learning models SLIM and EASE, alongside ADMM. Originally designed for item-item similarity learning, SLIM and EASE can adapt to learn user-user similarities by transposing the user-item interaction matrix R . *For our purposes, focusing on user-user similarities, we directly define R as an item-user interaction matrix to streamline notation and eliminate the need for constant transposing.* Table 1 outlines our notation with sets denoted by calligraphic letters or $\{\cdot\}$, vectors by bold lowercase, and matrices by bold uppercase.

3.1 Sparse Linear Methods (SLIM)

SLIM [35] optimizes a least-squares regression model with elastic net regularization, yielding sparse similarity estimates for each user that represent its neighborhood. The acquired user-user similarities are then utilized as weights for the item vectors: for an arbitrary user

$u \in \mathcal{U}$ and item $i \in \mathcal{I}$, the ranking estimate is $\hat{r}_{iu} = \mathbf{r}_i \cdot \mathbf{w}_u$, where $\mathbf{w}_u \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{U}|}$ the similarity weights of user u relative to all users. Ranking estimates for unobserved items are ranked in descending order, recommending the top-N. The similarities are computed by solving the following optimization problem:

$$\mathbf{W}^* = \arg \min_{\mathbf{W}} \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{R} - \mathbf{R}\mathbf{W}\|_F^2 + \lambda_1 \|\mathbf{W}\|_1 + \frac{\lambda_2}{2} \|\mathbf{W}\|_F^2 \quad (1)$$

s.t. $\text{diag}(\mathbf{W}) = \mathbf{0}$ and $\mathbf{W} \geq 0$,

where $\mathbf{W} = [\mathbf{w}_1, \dots, \mathbf{w}_{|\mathcal{U}|}] \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{U}| \times |\mathcal{U}|}$ the user-user similarity matrix and $\lambda_1, \lambda_2 > 0$ the regularization parameters.

The first term minimizes reconstruction error, the second term introduces sparsity to form the neighborhoods, and the third term introduces smoothness to prevent overfitting. The first constraint, the *self-similarity constraint*, prevents self-similarity by ensuring $\mathbf{W}^* \neq \mathbf{I}_{|\mathcal{U}|}$. The second, the *non-negativity constraint*, allows only positive relations between users to enhance interpretability.

3.2 Embarrassingly Shallow AutoEncoders (EASE)

Steck [41] omitted the sparsity-enforcing regularization and the non-negativity constraint, resulting in a new model called EASE. The similarities result from the following optimization:

$$\mathbf{W}^* = \arg \min_{\mathbf{W}} \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{R} - \mathbf{R}\mathbf{W}\|_F^2 + \frac{\lambda_2}{2} \|\mathbf{W}\|_F^2 \quad \text{s.t.} \quad \text{diag}(\mathbf{W}) = \mathbf{0}. \quad (2)$$

This simplification allows EASE to benefit from a closed-form solution, a feature SLIM lacks. EASE leads to increased ranking accuracy and is faster due to the direct computation of similarities enabled by the closed-form solution [42].

3.3 Alternating Direction Method of Multipliers (ADMM)

ADMM, popular for its ability to decompose complex optimization problems, is widely used in various domains [4], including recommenders [10, 42]. It is a first-order optimization method for optimizing problems of the form:

$$\min_{\mathbf{W}, \mathbf{Z}} f(\mathbf{W}) + g(\mathbf{Z}) \quad \text{s.t.} \quad \mathbf{A}\mathbf{W} + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{Z} = \mathbf{C}, \quad (3)$$

where f and g are convex closed functions; \mathbf{W} and \mathbf{Z} are the unknown matrices of variables to be optimized; and \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} , and \mathbf{C} are coefficient matrices defining the optimization constraint.

The solution procedure can be simplified by minimizing the augmented Lagrangian of the above-given problem. This function merges the primal and dual problems, i.e., the original objective function and its constraint, into one:

$$\mathcal{L}_\rho(\mathbf{W}, \mathbf{Z}, \mathbf{Y}) = f(\mathbf{W}) + g(\mathbf{Z}) + \frac{\rho}{2} \|\mathbf{A}\mathbf{W} + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{Z} - \mathbf{C}\|_F^2 + \langle \mathbf{Y}, (\mathbf{A}\mathbf{W} + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{Z} - \mathbf{C}) \rangle, \quad (4)$$

where $\rho > 0$ is a parameter that controls the trade-off between the accuracy of the solution and the convergence rate of the algorithm. \mathbf{Y} denotes the matrix of Lagrangian multipliers, representing the magnitude of the constraint violation.

In ADMM, the augmented Lagrangian is minimized through an iterative process that gradually converges towards the solution,

Table 1: Notation and Definitions.

Symbol	Description	Symbol	Description
\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{I}	Sets of user and item identifiers	\oslash	Element-wise division
$ \cdot $	The size of a set	\odot	Element-wise multiplication (Hadamard product)
\mathbf{R}	The $ \mathcal{I} \times \mathcal{U} $ interaction matrix	$\ \mathbf{W}\ _F^2$	Squared Frobenius norm of \mathbf{W}
$\mathbf{r}_i, \mathbf{r}_u$	Row and column vectors of \mathbf{R}	$\ \mathbf{W}\ _1$	Sum of the absolute elements of \mathbf{W}
$\text{Diag}(\boldsymbol{\gamma})$	Diagonal matrix with elements of vector $\boldsymbol{\gamma}$	$\ \mathbf{W}\ _\infty$	Maximum absolute value in \mathbf{W}
$\text{diag}(\mathbf{W})$	Vector of diagonal elements of matrix \mathbf{W}	$\mathbf{1}_{\text{condition}}$	Indicator function, 1 if condition is true, otherwise 0
$\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$	Frobenius inner product	$\ \mathbf{a}\ _2^2$	Squared Euclidean norm of vector \mathbf{a}
$s_\tau(\cdot)$	Soft-thresholding operator with threshold τ	$(\cdot)_+$	Positive part operator

entailing three sequential updates in each iteration k :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{W}^{k+1} &= \arg \min_{\mathbf{W}} \mathcal{L}_\rho(\mathbf{W}, \mathbf{Z}^k, \mathbf{Y}^k), \\ \mathbf{Z}^{k+1} &= \arg \min_{\mathbf{Z}} \mathcal{L}_\rho(\mathbf{W}^{k+1}, \mathbf{Z}, \mathbf{Y}^k), \text{ and} \\ \mathbf{Y}^{k+1} &= \mathbf{Y}^k + \rho(\mathbf{A}\mathbf{W}^{k+1} + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{Z}^{k+1} - \mathbf{C}). \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

The steps outlined in Eq. (5) are repeated until convergence or a maximum iteration limit is reached.

4 BALANCED NEIGHBORHOODS

In this section, we first revisit BNSLIM's objective and then reformulate it for simultaneous optimization of all similarities through the ADMM framework. While presented for *C-fairness through balanced user neighborhoods*, BNSLIM can also achieve *P-fairness through balanced item neighborhoods* by transposing \mathbf{R} .

4.1 Balanced Neighborhood SLIM (BNSLIM)

BNSLIM attempts to learn a matrix of user-user relationships, with the goal that each user can be represented equally by users from two distinct demographic groups: the protected \mathcal{G}_p , which is subject to bias, and the non-protected \mathcal{G}_{np} . Specifically, it aims for each user to be equally influenced by members from both of these groups in the resultant similarity matrix. The optimization problem of BNSLIM for synthesizing this balanced matrix \mathbf{W}^* is formulated as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{W}^* &= \arg \min_{\mathbf{W}} \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{R} - \mathbf{R}\mathbf{W}\|_F^2 + \lambda_1 \|\mathbf{W}\|_1 + \frac{\lambda_2}{2} \|\mathbf{W}\|_F^2 \\ &+ \frac{\lambda_3}{2} \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}} (\mathbf{p}^\top \mathbf{w}_{\cdot u})^2 \text{ s.t. } \text{diag}(\mathbf{W}) = \mathbf{0} \text{ and } \mathbf{W} \geq 0, \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{W} = [\mathbf{w}_{\cdot 1}, \dots, \mathbf{w}_{\cdot |\mathcal{U}|}] \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{U}| \times |\mathcal{U}|}$ is the user-user similarity matrix; $\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{U}|}$ is a vector with 1 for members of \mathcal{G}_p and -1 for \mathcal{G}_{np} ; and $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3 > 0$ are the regularization parameters.

The inclusion of the non-negativity constraint in BNSLIM prevents offsetting similarities within \mathcal{G}_p and \mathcal{G}_{np} , ensuring that positive and negative influences do not cancel each other out.

Removing the fourth term from Eq. (6), known as the balanced regularization term, transforms BNSLIM back into SLIM [35], omitting its capability to learn balanced neighborhoods.

The optimization problem defined in Eq. (6) is typically solved using Coordinate Descent (CD) [7]. For each distinct user pair (u, v) ,

where $u \neq v$, the similarity is iteratively updated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} w_{uv} &= \frac{(s_{\lambda_1}(C_{uv}))_+}{\sum_{i=1}^{|\mathcal{I}|} r_{io}^2 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_3}, \\ \text{with } C_{uv} &= \sum_{i=1}^{|\mathcal{I}|} (r_{iu} - \sum_{l=1, l \neq u, v}^{|\mathcal{U}|} r_{il} w_{lu}) + \lambda_3 p_v \sum_{l=1, l \neq u, v}^{|\mathcal{U}|} p_l w_{lu}. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

From Eq. (7), it is clear that individually optimizing each similarity presents computational challenges, especially for large user bases. To enhance performance, BNSLIM updates similarities between the closest neighbors only, predefined and fixed throughout the algorithm [6]. Still, this heuristic does not lead to notable performance gains and results in suboptimal solutions [3].

To address this, we propose rewriting Eq. (6) to express the balanced regularization term in a compact matrix form, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{W}^* &= \arg \min_{\mathbf{W}} \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{R} - \mathbf{R}\mathbf{W}\|_F^2 + \lambda_1 \|\mathbf{W}\|_1 + \frac{\lambda_2}{2} \|\mathbf{W}\|_F^2 \\ &+ \frac{\lambda_3}{2} \|\mathbf{p}^\top \mathbf{W}\|_2^2 \text{ s.t. } \text{diag}(\mathbf{W}) = \mathbf{0} \text{ and } \mathbf{W} \geq 0. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

We may now solve this optimization problem for the entire \mathbf{W} matrix, addressing the efficiency bottleneck of BNSLIM.

4.2 Optimization via ADMM

Under the ADMM framework, the augmented Lagrangian for the optimization problem in Eq. (8) is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_\rho(\mathbf{W}, \mathbf{Z}, \mathbf{Y}) &= \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{R} - \mathbf{R}\mathbf{W}\|_F^2 + \frac{\lambda_2}{2} \|\mathbf{W}\|_F^2 + \frac{\lambda_3}{2} \|\mathbf{p}^\top \mathbf{W}\|_2^2 + \underbrace{\lambda_1 \|\mathbf{Z}\|_1}_{g(\mathbf{Z})} \\ &+ \frac{\rho}{2} \|\mathbf{A}\mathbf{W} + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{Z} - \mathbf{C}\|_F^2 + \langle \mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{A}\mathbf{W} + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{Z} - \mathbf{C} \rangle, \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where $\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{I}_{|\mathcal{U}|}$ (the $|\mathcal{U}| \times |\mathcal{U}|$ identity matrix), $\mathbf{B} = -\mathbf{I}_{|\mathcal{U}|}$, and $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{O}_{|\mathcal{U}|}$ (the $|\mathcal{U}| \times |\mathcal{U}|$ matrix of zeroes).

The ADMM updating steps, as outlined in Section 3, can be adapted to accommodate the specificities of BNSLIM.

Step 1: \mathbf{W} update. The self-similarity constraint is enforced in the update process using Lagrange multipliers, penalizing the loss function upon violation. Thus, the new loss for updating \mathbf{W} is:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_\rho^{(c)}(\mathbf{W}, \mathbf{Z}^k, \mathbf{Y}^k) &= f(\mathbf{W}) + g(\mathbf{Z}^k) + \frac{\rho}{2} \|\mathbf{W} - \mathbf{Z}^k\|_F^2 \\ &+ \langle \mathbf{Y}^k, \mathbf{W} - \mathbf{Z}^k \rangle + \mathbf{y}^\top \text{diag}(\mathbf{W}), \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where $f(\cdot)$ includes all the involving differentiable norms² and $\boldsymbol{\gamma} \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{U}|}$ is the Lagrangian multiplier vector.

To determine the optimal solution, we set the partial derivative of $\mathcal{L}_\rho^{(c)}(\mathbf{W}, \mathbf{Z}^k, \mathbf{Y}^k)$ w.r.t. \mathbf{W} to zero, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{W}^{k+1} = \mathbf{Q}^k - P \text{Diag}(\boldsymbol{\gamma}), \quad (11)$$

where $\mathbf{Q}^k = P(G + \rho \mathbf{Z}^k - \mathbf{Y}^k)$, $P = (G + (\lambda_2 + \rho)I_{|\mathcal{U}|} + \lambda_3 \mathbf{P}\mathbf{P}^\top)^{-1}$, and $G = \mathbf{R}^\top \mathbf{R}$, the Gram matrix, indicating user-user similarities.

Given $\text{diag}(\mathbf{W}^{k+1}) = \mathbf{0}$, it follows that $\boldsymbol{\gamma} = \text{diag}(\mathbf{Q}^k) \odot \text{diag}(P)$. Therefore, Eq. (11) can be rewritten as:

$$\mathbf{W}^{k+1} = \mathbf{Q}^k - P \text{Diag}(\text{diag}(\mathbf{Q}^k) \odot \text{diag}(P)). \quad (12)$$

Step 2: Z update. Setting $\mathcal{L}_\rho(\mathbf{W}^{k+1}, \mathbf{Z}, \mathbf{Y}^k)$'s partial derivative w.r.t. \mathbf{Z} to zero involves handling the $\|\cdot\|_1$ norm, which is non-differentiable at zero. The soft-thresholding operator, $s_{\lambda_1/\rho}(\cdot)$, is applied to act as a proximal operator for the norm. We then project the output onto the non-negative orthant to preserve the non-negativity constraint. Thus, the update formula for \mathbf{Z} is:

$$\mathbf{Z}^{k+1} = \left(s_{\lambda_1/\rho}(\mathbf{W}^{k+1} + \frac{1}{\rho} \mathbf{Y}^k) \right)_+. \quad (13)$$

Step 3: Y update. Finally, $\mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{U}| \times |\mathcal{U}|}$ is updated as specified in Eq. (5). This update is crucial for ensuring that the variables \mathbf{W} and \mathbf{Z} , updated in the earlier steps, converge towards equality.

The ADMM update steps for Eq. (8) are outlined in Alg. 1.

5 FAIRLY SPARSE NEIGHBORHOODS

This section presents the FSLR model, aimed at *C-fairness through fairly sparse user neighborhoods*. FSLR can also achieve *P-fairness through fairly sparse item neighborhoods* by transposing \mathbf{R} .

5.1 Fairly Sparse Linear Regression (FSLR)

BNSLIM's balancing strategy may compromise accuracy by increasing (decreasing) the similarity scores with irrelevant (relevant) neighbors. To achieve fairness with minimal impact on personalization, we propose an alternative approach: induce controlled sparsity in neighborhoods to reveal *correlations* among users of different demographic groups. In particular, we introduce FSLR, a model designed to learn a partially, i.e., *fairly*, sparse matrix of user-user relationships, with the goal that each user is primarily represented as a linear combination of users from different groups. The similarities result from the following optimization:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{W}^* &= \arg \min_{\mathbf{W}} \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{R} - \mathbf{R}\mathbf{W}\|_F^2 + \lambda_1 \|\mathbf{M} \odot \mathbf{W}\|_1 + \frac{\lambda_2}{2} \|\mathbf{W}\|_F^2 \\ &\text{s.t. } \text{diag}(\mathbf{W}) = \mathbf{0}, \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where $\mathbf{M} = [\boldsymbol{\mu}_{\cdot 1}, \dots, \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\cdot |\mathcal{U}|}] \in \{0, 1\}^{|\mathcal{U}| \times |\mathcal{U}|}$ is a matrix with $\mu_{uv} = 1$ if user u belongs to the same group as user v and $\mu_{uv} = 0$ otherwise, $\forall u, v \in \mathcal{U}$; and $\lambda_1, \lambda_2 > 0$ are the regularization parameters.

Applying the non-negativity constraint to Eq. (14) modifies SLIM by enforcing elastic-net regularization within demographic groups. Omitting the second term of Eq. (14) reverts the model to its EASE form. The novelty lies in incorporating \mathbf{M} into the $\|\cdot\|_1$ norm, as λ_1 selectively reduces the influence of neighbors from the same group

² f combines EASE with the term for balance. Without $\|\cdot\|_1$ regularization, the task of balancing neighborhoods becomes challenging due to EASE's dense similarities.

on each individual user, facilitating the discovery of important relationships with users from different groups. Adding the balanced regularization term would introduce a conflict between prioritizing cross-group similarities (FSLR) and balancing group similarities (BNSLIM), justifying the proposal of two separate models.

5.2 Optimization via ADMM

Under the ADMM framework, the augmented Lagrangian for the optimization problem in Eq. (14) is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_\rho(\mathbf{W}, \mathbf{Z}, \mathbf{Y}) &= \overbrace{\frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{R} - \mathbf{R}\mathbf{W}\|_F^2}^{f(\mathbf{W})} + \frac{\lambda_2}{2} \|\mathbf{W}\|_F^2 + \underbrace{\lambda_1 \|\mathbf{M} \odot \mathbf{Z}\|_1}_{g(\mathbf{Z})} \\ &+ \frac{\rho}{2} \|\mathbf{A}\mathbf{W} + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{Z} - \mathbf{C}\|_F^2 + \langle \mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{A}\mathbf{W} + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{Z} - \mathbf{C} \rangle, \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where $\mathbf{A} = I_{|\mathcal{U}|}$ (the $|\mathcal{U}| \times |\mathcal{U}|$ identity matrix), $\mathbf{B} = -I_{|\mathcal{U}|}$, and $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{O}_{|\mathcal{U}|}$ (the $|\mathcal{U}| \times |\mathcal{U}|$ matrix of zeroes).

This formulation enables concurrent optimization of EASE's objective and our controlled sparsity objective, with the last two terms balancing discrepancies between these subproblems.

The ADMM updating steps, as outlined in Section 3, can be adapted to accommodate the specificities of FSLR.

Step 1: W update. The self-similarity constraint is enforced in the update process using Lagrange multipliers, penalizing the loss function upon violation. Thus, the new loss for updating \mathbf{W} is:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_\rho^{(c)}(\mathbf{W}, \mathbf{Z}^k, \mathbf{Y}^k) &= f(\mathbf{W}) + g(\mathbf{Z}^k) + \frac{\rho}{2} \|\mathbf{W} - \mathbf{Z}^k\|_F^2 \\ &+ \left\langle \mathbf{Y}^k, \mathbf{W} - \mathbf{Z}^k \right\rangle + \boldsymbol{\gamma}^\top \text{diag}(\mathbf{W}). \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

To determine the optimal solution, we set the partial derivative of $\mathcal{L}_\rho^{(c)}(\mathbf{W}, \mathbf{Z}^k, \mathbf{Y}^k)$ w.r.t. \mathbf{W} to zero, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{W}^{k+1} = \mathbf{Q}^k - P \text{Diag}(\boldsymbol{\gamma}), \quad (17)$$

where $\mathbf{Q}^k = P(G + \rho \mathbf{Z}^k - \mathbf{Y}^k)$, $P = (G + (\lambda_2 + \rho)I_{|\mathcal{U}|})^{-1}$, and $G = \mathbf{R}^\top \mathbf{R}$, the Gram matrix, indicating user-user similarities.

Given $\text{diag}(\mathbf{W}^{k+1}) = \mathbf{0}$, it follows that $\boldsymbol{\gamma} = \text{diag}(\mathbf{Q}^k) \odot \text{diag}(P)$. Therefore, Eq. (17) can be rewritten as:

$$\mathbf{W}^{k+1} = \mathbf{Q}^k - P \text{Diag}(\text{diag}(\mathbf{Q}^k) \odot \text{diag}(P)). \quad (18)$$

Step 2: Z update. By setting $\mathcal{L}_\rho(\mathbf{W}^{k+1}, \mathbf{Z}, \mathbf{Y}^k)$'s partial derivative w.r.t. \mathbf{Z} to zero, it follows that

$$\mathbf{Z}^{k+1} = s_{\lambda_1/\rho}(\mathbf{W}^{k+1} + \frac{1}{\rho} \mathbf{Y}^k) \odot \mathbf{M} + (\mathbf{W}^{k+1} + \frac{1}{\rho} \mathbf{Y}^k) \odot \tilde{\mathbf{M}}, \quad (19)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{M}} = \mathbf{J}_{|\mathcal{U}|} - \mathbf{M}$, with $\mathbf{J}_{|\mathcal{U}|}$ being a $|\mathcal{U}| \times |\mathcal{U}|$ matrix of ones, indicating $\tilde{\mathbf{M}}$ as the binary complement of \mathbf{M} .

This step penalizes updates to elements of \mathbf{Z} associated with users from the same group, while elements associated with users from different groups remain unaffected by the L1 regularizer.

Step 3: Y update. Finally, $\mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{U}| \times |\mathcal{U}|}$ is updated as specified in Eq. (5). This update is crucial for ensuring that the variables \mathbf{W} and \mathbf{Z} , updated in the earlier steps, converge towards equality.

The ADMM update steps for Eq. (14) are outlined in Alg. 2.

Complexities. BNSLIM has a complexity of $\mathcal{O}(k|\mathcal{U}|^3|I|)$ due to k iterations updating $|\mathcal{U}|^2$ similarities, each involving computations

Algorithm 1 BNSLIM via ADMM

Input: $R, p, \lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, \rho$ **Output:** $W^* = W^{k+1}$
Initialize: $k = 0, W^0 = Z^0$, and Y^0
 $G = R^T R, P = (G + (\lambda_2 + \rho)I_{|\mathcal{U}|} + \lambda_3 p p^T)^{-1}$
repeat
 $Q^k = P(G + \rho Z^k - Y^k)$
 $W^{k+1} = Q^k - P \text{Diag}(\text{diag}(Q^k) \odot \text{diag}(P))$
 $Z^{k+1} = (s_{\lambda_1/\rho}(W^{k+1} + \frac{1}{\rho} Y^k))_+$
 $Y^{k+1} = Y^k + \rho \cdot (W^{k+1} - Z^{k+1})$
 $k = k + 1$
until convergence

Algorithm 2 FSLR via ADMM

Input: $R, M, \lambda_1, \lambda_2, \rho$ **Output:** $W^* = W^{k+1}$
Initialize: $k = 0, W^0 = Z^0$, and Y^0
 $G = R^T R, P = (G + (\lambda_2 + \rho)I_{|\mathcal{U}|})^{-1}$
repeat
 $Q^k = P(G + \rho Z^k - Y^k)$
 $W^{k+1} = Q^k - P \text{Diag}(\text{diag}(Q^k) \odot \text{diag}(P))$
 $Z^{k+1} = s_{\lambda_1/\rho}(W^{k+1} + \frac{1}{\rho} Y^k) \odot M + (W^{k+1} + \frac{1}{\rho} Y^k) \odot \tilde{M}$
 $Y^{k+1} = Y^k + \rho \cdot (W^{k+1} - Z^{k+1})$
 $k = k + 1$
until convergence

Figure 1: Imbalances in Music Preferences Across Groups.

across all users and items. Conversely, both $\text{BNSLIM}_{\text{ADMM}}$ and FSLR have a simpler complexity of $\mathcal{O}(k|\mathcal{U}|^3)$. For item neighborhoods, complexities adjust by interchanging $|\mathcal{U}|$ and $|\mathcal{I}|$.

6 DATASETS AND METRICS

Datasets. For C-fairness, we cover two distinct recommendation applications: movies and music. For movies, we used the Movielens 1M (ML1M) dataset [19]. We transformed ratings (1 to 5) into binary format by interpreting ratings of 4 or higher as positive feedback [9, 41]. Users were grouped by *gender*, with females as the protected group and males as the non-protected group. For music, we focused on artist recommendations using the LastFM 1K (LFM1K) dataset [8]. For each user, we aggregated song plays per artist, and if the count exceeded the average play count of that user, it was marked as positive feedback for this artist by the user. Users were grouped by *age*, with those over 30 as the protected group and those 30 or younger as the non-protected group, following [31]. As LFM1K lacks music genre information, we used the genres extracted from MusicBrainz by [2]. In our analysis, we targeted genres where notable age imbalances among listeners were observed, specifically: *country*, *folk*, *hip hop*, *indie*, *jazz*, and *metal* (see Fig. 1).

For P-fairness, we also cover two distinct recommendation applications: courses and books. For courses, we used the COCO dataset [12], binarizing ratings (1 to 5) such that ratings of 5 are interpreted as positive feedback [2]. COCO features courses taught by teachers from various *geographic provinces*. We focused on courses by single teachers, grouping them as protected for teachers from developing countries and non-protected for those from developed countries, based on the OECD’s classification [36]. *To the best of our knowledge,*

this is the first exploration of bias in course recommendations based on teachers’ country development status. For books, we used the *young adult* subset of the Goodreads dataset [44], a genre where users exhibit bias based on *author’s gender* [43]. We retained books by single authors and binarized ratings (1 to 5) with ratings of 4 or higher considered as positive feedback. Subsequently, we fetched author gender (female or male) using the Wikidata API. Books were grouped by author gender, with male-written books viewed as protected and female-written books as non-protected.

Table 2 provides data statistics. All datasets underwent 10-core user filtering, i.e., keeping users with at least 10 interactions, to secure robust training data, and they were split: an 80-20 training-testing split and an additional 80-20 split within the training set for validation. For C-fairness, to ensure consistent group sizes across all splits, the datasets underwent *weak generalization*. This involves the same users appearing in all sets, a necessity for user-neighborhood models that cannot process unseen users. For P-fairness, we applied *strong generalization*, where users in each set are different, chosen to simulate real-world conditions, and because such a split would not notably alter the results, unlike in C-fairness.

Accuracy metrics. Accuracy is evaluated using *Recall* and *Normalized Discounted Cumulative Gain (NDCG)* [28, 31]. While both metrics evaluate the presence of held-out items in top-N recommendation lists, NDCG also accounts for their ranking positions. Higher scores on these metrics indicate better accuracy.

C-fairness metrics. Recall that C-fairness is defined as balancing the exposure of item groups across user groups. In our datasets, these item groups represent item categories: movie genres (ML1M dataset) and music genres (LFM1K dataset). In what follows, we describe two different aspects of this fairness objective.

Consumer-side Equity (c-Equity) [7] measures the ratio of the observed probability of recommending an item category to protected users (\mathcal{G}_p) relative to that of non-protected users (\mathcal{G}_{np}). For convenience, as c-Equity is computed separately for each item category, we reformulated it as the absolute difference between the observed probabilities, averaged across all categories, i.e.,

$$c\text{-Equity}@N = \frac{1}{|C|} \sum_{c \in C} |\Delta p_c|, \text{ with}$$

$$\Delta p_c = \frac{\sum_{u \in \mathcal{G}_p} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{R}_u} \mathbf{1}_{i \in C_c}}{|\mathcal{G}_p| \cdot N} - \frac{\sum_{u \in \mathcal{G}_{np}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{R}_u} \mathbf{1}_{i \in C_c}}{|\mathcal{G}_{np}| \cdot N}, \quad (20)$$

where C is the set of item category identifiers, \mathcal{R}_u is the top-N list for user u , and C_c includes all item identifiers related to c .

Table 2: Summary of Processed Data (\mathcal{G}_p : protected group, \mathcal{G}_{np} : non-protected group, $inter(\cdot)$: interaction counts).

Dataset	Fairness	Attribute	Sparsity	$ \mathcal{U} $	$ \mathcal{I} $	$ \mathcal{G}_p $	$ \mathcal{G}_{np} $	$inter(\mathcal{G}_p)$	$inter(\mathcal{G}_{np})$
ML1M	Consumer	Gender	97.27	5,950	3,532	1,682	4,268	145,372	429,247
LFM1K	Consumer	Age	98.01	236	2,233	37	199	2,032	8,003
COCO	Provider	Province	99.81	3,803	7,972	2,146	5,826	13,349	45,159
Goodreads	Provider	Gender	99.88	186,919	26,576	6,574	20,002	1,170,604	4,802,037

Scores range from 0 to 1, indicating the average difference in the visibility of item categories between two user groups. A score of 1 indicates a rare scenario where \mathcal{G}_p exclusively gets recommendations from one item category and \mathcal{G}_{np} from a different item category, with no overlap. A c-Equity score, multiplied by N, represents the average additional number of positions occupied by any item category in the top-N recommendation lists of a user group.

User-coverage Parity (u-Parity) measures the disparity between the proportions of users from \mathcal{G}_p and \mathcal{G}_{np} receiving recommendations from an item category, averaged across all categories, i.e.,

$$u\text{-Parity}@N = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{C}|} \sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}} |\Delta\pi_c|, \text{ with}$$

$$\Delta\pi_c = \frac{\sum_{u \in \mathcal{G}_p} \mathbf{1}_{\exists i \in \mathcal{R}_u : i \in \mathcal{C}_c}}{|\mathcal{G}_p|} - \frac{\sum_{u \in \mathcal{G}_{np}} \mathbf{1}_{\exists i \in \mathcal{R}_u : i \in \mathcal{C}_c}}{|\mathcal{G}_{np}|}. \quad (21)$$

Scores range from 0 to 1, with 0 indicating that equal percentages of users (from both groups) receive recommendations from each item category and 1 indicating a rare scenario where each item category covers users from only one group.

c-Equity helps identify if there is an imbalance in how item categories are recommended to distinct user groups, whereas u-Parity helps identify if there is an imbalance in how different user groups are covered by recommendations across categories.

P-fairness metrics. Recall that P-fairness is defined as balancing the exposure of item groups within the top-N lists of all users. In our datasets, these item groups represent providers: teachers (COCO dataset) and authors (Goodreads dataset). In what follows, we describe two different aspects of this fairness objective.

Bilateral Disparate Visibility (BDV) is a modification of the c-Equity metric for P-fairness. BDV measures the difference between the observed probability of recommending protected items (\mathcal{G}_p) and that of non-protected items (\mathcal{G}_{np}), i.e.,

$$BDV@N = \left| \frac{\sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{R}_u} \mathbf{1}_{i \in \mathcal{G}_p}}{|\mathcal{U}| \cdot N} - \frac{\sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{R}_u} \mathbf{1}_{i \in \mathcal{G}_{np}}}{|\mathcal{U}| \cdot N} \right|. \quad (22)$$

Scores range from 0 (balanced visibility) to 1 (imbalanced visibility), indicating the difference in visibility between protected and non-protected items in top-N recommendation lists.

A BDV score, multiplied by N, represents the additional number of positions occupied by one group over another.

Average Provider Coverage Rate (APCR) [29] measures the degree of provider coverage within the recommendation lists of all users in the test set. APCR is formally defined as follows:

$$APCR@N = \frac{\sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}_{\text{test}}} \text{prov}(\mathcal{R}_u)}{|\mathcal{P}| |\mathcal{U}_{\text{test}}|}, \quad (23)$$

where $\mathcal{U}_{\text{test}}$ is the user set in the test dataset, $\text{prov}(\mathcal{R}_u)$ counts distinct providers in \mathcal{R}_u , and \mathcal{P} is the set of providers.

In our datasets, we have two providers: the protected and non-protected teachers or authors, i.e., $|\mathcal{P}| = 2$.

Scores range from 0 to 1. A score of 0 indicates a lack of coverage, with recommendations dominated by a single provider group, while a score of 1 indicates perfect coverage, with all providers appearing across all top-N recommendation lists.

u-Parity and APCR metrics emphasize coverage fairness in top-N recommendation lists. Specifically, u-Parity evaluates balanced item category access for different consumer groups, while APCR evaluates balanced provider appearance for all consumers.

7 BENCHMARKING AND RESULTS

The evaluation of our algorithms regarding C- and P-fairness is guided by the following research questions:

- RQ1.** Can our algorithms achieve C- and P-fairness? What is the impact on accuracy?
- RQ2.** How do they compare to other fairness-aware algorithms in terms of fairness, accuracy, and time efficiency?
- RQ3.** How do the different characteristics and sensitive attributes of datasets affect our algorithms' behavior?

Competitors. We consider two baselines. EASE, as a SOTA lacking fairness capabilities, benchmarks our fairness improvements. BNSLIM, the sole existing fairness-aware neighborhood-learning algorithm, emphasizes the demand for our more efficient alternatives. We utilize both the user- and item-neighborhood versions of EASE for C- and P-fairness experiments, respectively. Two advanced fairness-aware algorithms are also considered. *Fair Matrix Factorization (FairMF)* [46] is the classical MF model enhanced with the *non-parity regularizer* of [22], chosen for its interpretability when binary data are present and its frequent use in related work [25, 45]. *Fairness-aware Data Augmentation (FDA)* using *Bayesian Personalized Ranking (BPR)* as its backbone [9], chosen as the most recent data-driven fairness strategy, akin to the proposed algorithms. BNSLIM and FairMF are applicable for both C- and P-fairness. FDA, originally designed for C-fairness, presents challenges in applying for P-fairness; hence, we use it solely for C-fairness.

Implementations. Neighborhood-learning algorithms were implemented using *Recpack* [32]. Our Python implementation for BNSLIM adheres to its original Java version [6]. For FDA, we used the implementation available by its authors³. We implemented FairMF in *PyTorch* [37], due to the lack of existing code.

Fine-tuning. We used *Hyperopt* [23] to optimize for $N = 10$. The parameter spaces for the competitors were set based on their

³<https://github.com/newlei/FDA>

Table 3: Results on the ML1M and LFM1K Datasets (top-10 lists). Best metric scores are presented in bold, while the slowest training times are marked in red. Rows corresponding to our algorithms are shaded in purple for easy identification.

Algorithm	ML1M					LFM1K				
	Training (secs)	Accuracy Metrics		Fairness Metrics		Training (secs)	Accuracy Metrics		Fairness Metrics	
		Recall \uparrow	NDCG \uparrow	c-Equity \downarrow	u-Parity \downarrow		Recall \uparrow	NDCG \uparrow	c-Equity \downarrow	u-Parity \downarrow
EASE	6.854 (2.786)	0.323 (0.001)	0.332 (0.000)	0.050 (0.001)	0.097 (0.001)	0.041 (0.017)	0.222 (0.006)	0.208 (0.008)	0.060 (0.004)	0.108 (0.014)
BNSLIM	11,160.704 (3,597.703)	0.239 (0.007)	0.246 (0.006)	0.038 (0.001)	0.066 (0.002)	478.099 (25.274)	0.142 (0.027)	0.127 (0.023)	0.031 (0.012)	0.060 (0.013)
BNSLIM _{ADMM}	120.580 (4.490)	0.226 (0.013)	0.240 (0.016)	0.015 (0.004)	0.027 (0.005)	0.085 (0.026)	0.116 (0.004)	0.098 (0.007)	0.010 (0.004)	0.026 (0.008)
FSLR	60.893 (39.747)	0.255 (0.010)	0.270 (0.010)	0.026 (0.007)	0.059 (0.007)	0.055 (0.018)	0.164 (0.010)	0.151 (0.009)	0.039 (0.007)	0.114 (0.034)
FairMF	5.878 (3.042)	0.161 (0.015)	0.164 (0.019)	0.013 (0.002)	0.028 (0.003)	0.201 (0.169)	0.103 (0.049)	0.092 (0.045)	0.016 (0.004)	0.039 (0.007)
FDA	3,156.129 (807.204)	0.250 (0.023)	0.251 (0.025)	0.057 (0.003)	0.118 (0.007)	45.212 (10.284)	0.159 (0.011)	0.145 (0.016)	0.060 (0.007)	0.116 (0.011)

Table 4: Results on the COCO and Goodreads Datasets (top-10 lists). Best metric scores are presented in bold, while the slowest training times are marked in red. Rows corresponding to our algorithms are shaded in purple for easy identification.

Algorithm	COCO					Goodreads				
	Training (secs)	Accuracy Metrics		Fairness Metrics		Training (secs)	Accuracy Metrics		Fairness Metrics	
		Recall \uparrow	NDCG \uparrow	BDV \downarrow	APCR \uparrow		Recall \uparrow	NDCG \uparrow	BDV \downarrow	APCR \uparrow
EASE	7.863 (0.945)	0.275 (0.005)	0.214 (0.005)	0.586 (0.013)	0.870 (0.010)	117.301 (15.450)	0.554 (0.001)	0.529 (0.001)	0.527 (0.001)	0.898 (0.001)
BNSLIM	33,237.556 (5,116.273)	0.031 (0.006)	0.020 (0.007)	0.680 (0.094)	0.873 (0.051)	<i>- did not complete within the 24-hour limit -</i>				
BNSLIM _{ADMM}	160.103 (69.683)	0.153 (0.047)	0.129 (0.038)	0.207 (0.265)	0.831 (0.038)	3,435.894 (21.644)	0.498 (0.009)	0.470 (0.008)	0.482 (0.010)	0.916 (0.004)
FSLR	182.845 (50.534)	0.197 (0.021)	0.157 (0.014)	0.079 (0.040)	0.898 (0.012)	2,009.628 (1,540.767)	0.499 (0.005)	0.472 (0.004)	0.476 (0.004)	0.917 (0.002)
FairMF	24.040 (16.832)	0.002 (0.001)	0.001 (0.000)	0.437 (0.021)	0.983 (0.005)	1,424.151 (812.837)	0.000 (0.000)	0.000 (0.000)	0.449 (0.035)	0.980 (0.006)

respective papers. For BNSLIM_{ADMM}, the parameter space included λ_1 ranging from 10^{-3} to 50, λ_2 from 1 to 10^4 , and λ_3 from 10^{-3} to 10^3 . For FSLR, the parameter space was set for λ_1 from 10^{-3} to 10 and λ_2 from 1 to 10^4 . The *Tree-structured Parzen Estimator (TPE)* algorithm guided this process, limited to either 50 trials or 24 hours. Convergence for BNSLIM was set at $\|W^k - W^{k+1}\|_\infty < 10^{-4}$ or 50 iterations, while for BNSLIM_{ADMM} and FSLR, it was set at $\|W^{k+1} - Z^{k+1}\|_\infty < 10^{-4}$ or 50 iterations. To enhance the computational efficiency of BNSLIM, we used a cap of 100 neighbors.

Addressing the lack of standard fairness optimization and the frequent omission of such details in existing studies and code repositories, we explain our own approach. Given our interest in both accuracy and fairness, it was deemed reasonable to tune all fairness-aware algorithms by combining NDCG (accuracy) with c-Equity or BDV for C- or P-fairness, respectively. This combination was formulated as $\alpha \times (1 - \text{accuracy}@N) + (1 - \alpha) \times \text{fairness}@N$, where α is a weighting parameter that allows system designers to tailor the balance between accuracy and fairness according to marketplace needs. Prioritizing fairness in this work, we chose $\alpha = 0.2$, and accordingly tuned all fairness-aware algorithms using this configuration. Conversely, EASE was tuned solely based on NDCG.

Experiments ran on an Ubuntu server featuring an Intel[®] Xeon[®] Gold 5318Y processor at 2.10GHz with 48 cores and 386GB of RAM.

The code for the experiments is available on GitHub⁴.

7.1 C-fairness Results

Each experiment was repeated five times to ensure reliability. Table 3 details the mean performance and standard deviation for each metric. Note that the small fairness scores are the result of balancing

the exposure of multiple item categories within the top-10 lists amidst the inherent diversity of user interests within each group.

RQ1. In both datasets, our BNSLIM_{ADMM} considerably improves fairness compared to EASE over its predecessor, BNSLIM, both in terms of item group exposure (c-Equity) and user coverage (u-Parity), while preserving accuracy losses comparable to those observed between BNSLIM and EASE. In the LFM1K dataset, it reduced the c-Equity score from 6% to 1% compared to EASE, implying a nearly negligible disparity in the representation of each item category across top-N recommendation lists for different user groups. This favorably impacted the u-Parity metric, decreasing from 10.8% to 2.6%, which shows more even user coverage by each category. Similar reductions are observed in the ML1M dataset. However, in the LFM1K dataset, these improvements lead to a recall and NDCG reduction of about 48-53% from EASE.

FSLR improves fairness while achieving the least reduction in ranking accuracy from EASE in both datasets. FSLR’s superior accuracy over BNSLIM_{ADMM} is attributed to the latter’s stringent approach to balancing neighborhoods: by increasing (decreasing) the similarity scores with irrelevant (relevant) neighbors for the sake of influence balance, i.e., it may increase (potentially artificially) fairness but adversely affect personalization, as shown by the significant decrease in recall and NDCG of BNSLIM_{ADMM}.

Answer to RQ1. *Our algorithms effectively enhance C-fairness in neighborhood learning, with FSLR compromising less accuracy than BNSLIM_{ADMM}, following a more reasonable approach for fairness.*

RQ2. EASE leads in accuracy, while BNSLIM_{ADMM} and FairMF are more fair, sacrificing accuracy. BNSLIM_{ADMM} achieves the best fairness scores compared to all fairness-aware competitors in both datasets, followed by FairMF, which slightly surpasses BNSLIM_{ADMM} in ML1M, achieving the best c-Equity score. FairMF is also the

⁴https://github.com/Selefth/fair_neighborhood

fastest but ranks last in terms of personalization, making it less appealing for imposing fairness due to its high accuracy loss.

Apart from improved fairness, BNSLIM_{ADMM} has another notable advantage over BNSLIM: it is orders of magnitude faster. For instance, for the ML1M dataset, it achieves a reduction of about 99% in training time, where 5,950² similarities must be learned. BNSLIM, in contrast, only computes 100 neighbors per user to manage its computational load, highlighting BNSLIM_{ADMM}'s superior efficiency in processing the full set of similarities more rapidly. Among the two algorithms, BNSLIM_{ADMM} is a more efficient choice for attaining fairness through balanced neighborhoods.

FDA is also time-intensive due to its data-augmentation approach. This model underperformed in our C-fairness context, as even if the estimated interactions are balanced, some item categories may still be underrepresented or overrepresented in the recommendations provided to different user groups. Our FSLR is faster than BNSLIM_{ADMM}, and, while not as strong in fairness as BNSLIM_{ADMM}, leads in accuracy among fairness-aware methods.

Answer to RQ2. *Compared to other fairness-aware methods, our algorithms demonstrate optimal performance in balancing accuracy, fairness, and reasonable training time.*

RQ3. FSLR surpasses BNSLIM in fairness metrics in ML1M but not in LFM1K, while securing the best ranking accuracy among fairness-aware methods. This variation could be due to the protected group's size in LFM1K, affecting FSLR's ability to form strong neighbor relations with users from different groups. On the other hand, BNSLIM_{ADMM} consistently outperforms BNSLIM in fairness in both datasets, as, in contrast to BNSLIM, it considers all possible neighbors to achieve balance. Lastly, FSLR consistently achieves accuracy closer to that of EASE.

Answer to RQ3. *Our comparison with EASE revealed that our algorithms are consistent in reducing unfairness in the ML1M and LFM1K datasets, focusing on distinct sensitive attributes: users' genders and users' ages, respectively.*

7.2 P-fairness Results

Each experiment was repeated five times to ensure reliability. Table 4 details the mean performance outcomes for each metric, along with their corresponding standard deviations. P-fairness scores are larger compared to their C-fairness counterparts due to our focus on only two item groups, making any disparities more noticeable.

RQ1. In the COCO dataset, EASE's 58.6% overrepresentation of courses from developed countries (BDV), translating to roughly six more slots for developed countries in users' top-10 lists, is notably reduced by our algorithms: BNSLIM_{ADMM} reduces this to 20.7% and FSLR further decreases it to 7.9%. The high standard deviation in BNSLIM_{ADMM}'s BDV score suggests a sensitivity to strong generalization, unlike FSLR. This also contributes to its slightly poorer (compared to EASE) APCR. Despite the fairness gains, there are accuracy trade-offs: Compared to EASE, BNSLIM_{ADMM} shows a drop in accuracy by nearly 40-44%, whereas FSLR by about 27-28%. In the Goodreads dataset, EASE exhibits a 52.7% overrepresentation of women-authored books. While our mitigation methods' impact is not as pronounced as in COCO, both of them managed to reduce this imbalance to 48%, with a 2% increase in APCR. Accuracy for both algorithms falls by 10-11% compared to EASE.

Answer to RQ1. *Our algorithms effectively enhance P-fairness, with FSLR compromising less accuracy than BNSLIM_{ADMM} in the COCO dataset, following the trends in C-fairness. Strong generalization impacts BNSLIM_{ADMM}'s performance.*

RQ2. BNSLIM exhibits poor performance, ranking as the slowest among all evaluated algorithms and failing to complete within the 24-hour limit on Goodreads. BNSLIM_{ADMM} outperforms BNSLIM with an impressive 99% reduction in training time for COCO and completes training on Goodreads, where BNSLIM could not. It also surpasses BNSLIM in both accuracy and fairness, establishing itself as a feasible solution for balancing neighborhoods.

FSLR achieves the best BDV score in COCO, notably improving over EASE. In both datasets, it shows strong APCR performance and surpasses all other fairness-aware methods in accuracy. BNSLIM_{ADMM} ranks near FSLR in fairness, but for the COCO dataset, it offers less personalized recommendations.

FairMF leads in APCR for both datasets and BDV for Goodreads, yet it underperforms in personalization, attributed to datasets' sparsity (see Table 2). Experiments on denser COCO subsets showed accuracy and fairness gains for FairMF, yet our algorithms preserved a superior balance of both (results omitted due to space limitations). FairMF is slower in Goodreads than in COCO, mainly due to its dependence on the number of users, while the item-neighborhood versions of our algorithms scale solely with the number of items.

Answer to RQ2. *Compared to other fairness-aware methods, our algorithms optimally balance accuracy and fairness while scaling well to large datasets in P-fairness scenarios, with scalability driven solely by the number of items. Additionally, they demonstrate robust performance on sparse datasets, where other algorithms struggle.*

RQ3. BNSLIM_{ADMM} and FSLR reduce unfairness, more notably in the COCO dataset, possibly due to Goodreads' extensive volume of interactions (nearly 6 million). Extending training beyond 50 iterations would enhance fairness further. BNSLIM_{ADMM} is faster than FSLR in COCO, but it needs more time to converge in the larger Goodreads. Finally, in COCO, FSLR achieves better visibility (BDV score), whereas in Goodreads, both algorithms go hand-in-hand.

Answer to RQ3. *Our algorithms consistently reduce unfairness in both datasets, addressing distinct sensitive attributes: teachers' country (COCO dataset) and authors' genders (Goodreads dataset).*

8 CONCLUSIONS

We introduced two algorithms, BNSLIM_{ADMM} and FSLR, to address demographic bias in neighborhood-learning models, targeting group fairness for consumers or providers. BNSLIM_{ADMM} improves upon BNSLIM by employing the ADMM so as to balance the influences across demographic groups faster. FSLR induces controlled sparsity in neighborhoods, ensuring representation by demographically varied, yet correlated, counterparts so as to preserve personalization. We verified our algorithms empirically on several real-world datasets and showed that they outperformed existing solutions while achieving an optimal balance of accuracy, fairness, and time efficiency. An interesting research direction for future work involves developing algorithms for multi-group neighborhood balancing and exploring how these neighborhoods can preserve fairness while dynamically adapting to temporal changes.

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